

1 **Online measurement of floc size, viscosity, and consistency of cellulose** 2 **microfibril suspensions with optical coherence tomography**

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13 **Abstract**

14 In this study, cellulose microfibril (CMF) suspensions were imaged during pipe flow at consistencies
15 of 0.4%, 1.0%, and 1.6% with optical coherence tomography (OCT) to obtain images of the structure
16 and the local velocity of the suspension. The viscosities obtained by combining pressure loss
17 measurement with the OCT velocity data showed typical shear thinning behavior and were in
18 excellent agreement with viscosities obtained with ultrasound velocity profiling. The structural OCT
19 images were used to calculate the radial and the axial floc sizes of the suspension. A fit of power law
20 to the geometrical floc size–shear stress data gave the same power law index for all consistencies,
21 suggesting that floc rupture dynamics is independent of consistency. The dependence of viscosity and
22 floc size on shear stress was similar, indicating that the shear thinning behavior of CMF suspensions
23 is closely related to the rupture dynamics of flocs. The results also showed that an apparent attenuation
24 coefficient of the OCT signal can be used to determine the consistency of CMF suspensions.

25 **Introduction**

26 Cellulose microfibrils (CMFs) are a sustainable and a biodegradable material that make it possible to
27 develop novel, all-cellulose products due to, for instance, its lightness, mechanical robustness, and
28 barrier properties (Klemm et al. 2011; Lavoine et al. 2012; Moon et al. 2016). CMFs are already
29 being utilized in many applications, such as to reinforce paper and composite materials (Cheng et al.
30 2019; Lu et al. 2008; Øyvind Eriksen et al. 2008), in various membranes and barrier films (Lavoine
31 et al. 2012; Sharma et al. 2020), as a rheology modifier (Dimic-Misic et al. 2013; Li et al. 2015), and
32 in energy-storage devices (Kim et al. 2019). CMFs are obtained from wood or plant cells through a
33 chemical, enzymatic, or mechanical homogenization process (Desmaisons et al. 2017; Nechyporchuk

34 et al. 2016). The cellulose fibers are at that point broken down into bundles of individual CMF fibrils.
35 The size distribution of the fibrils obtained is broad and varies a great deal depending on the
36 disintegration process. Typically, the fibrils exhibit diameters at a scale of tens of nanometers and
37 length to diameter ratios (aspect ratios) in the hundreds. The specific surface area (and, thus, hydroxyl
38 group surface density) is much higher for CMF fibrils than for regular cellulose fibers. For these
39 reasons, CMFs easily form networks that are often encountered as flocs, gels, and films, and therefore,
40 the gross structure of the CMF suspensions is much larger than the size of individual fibrils (Hubbe
41 et al. 2017; Karppinen et al. 2012; Pääkkönen et al. 2016; Raj et al. 2017).

42 The raw CMF material is usually suspended in water before and during processing and production.
43 Rheological characterization of the CMF suspensions is a widely discussed topic and is relevant from
44 both practical and academic standpoints (Hubbe et al. 2017; Iotti et al. 2011; Kumar et al. 2016;
45 Mohtaschemi et al. 2014; Schenker et al. 2019; Tatsumi et al. 2002). Generally, CMF suspensions
46 are shear-thinning power law fluids—their viscosity is, *i.e.*, given with a good accuracy by the
47 formula

$$48 \quad \mu = K \dot{\gamma}^{n-1}, \quad (1)$$

49 where $\dot{\gamma}$ is the shear rate, K is the consistency index, and $n < 1$ is the flow index (Honorato et al.
50 2015; Lasseguette et al. 2008; Mohtaschemi et al. 2014). The viscosity dependence of CMF
51 suspensions on consistency is similar for different CMF grades (Koponen 2020). This similarity is
52 likely due to the flow dynamics of CMF suspensions not being that of individual fibrils but of flocs
53 dispersed in a liquid phase or in a gel-like matrix (Hubbe et al. 2017; Saarikoski et al. 2012).

54 CMF suspensions have a strong tendency to slip flow at solid walls (Nechyporchuk et al. 2014;
55 Turpeinen et al. 2020). The slip is caused by a wall depletion layer, where the consistency changes
56 from a nearly fibril-free zone to bulk consistency (Kataja et al. 2017; Lauri et al. 2017; Saarinen et
57 al. 2014). The slip behavior between CMF grades can be quite different and often causes problems in
58 rheometers by making it challenging to obtain reliable information about shear rheology (Haavisto et
59 al. 2015; Schenker et al. 2018; Turpeinen et al. 2020; Vadodaria et al. 2018). In addition to slip
60 behavior, sample preparation and shear history may also change the properties of the CMF and can
61 make reliable and repeatable characterizations of them difficult (Liao et al. 2020; Naderi and
62 Lindström 2015).

63 Dynamic flocculation and slip phenomena affect the rheological properties of suspensions in the
64 processing industry and often dictate the product quality and properties, process performance, and

65 economics (Raj et al. 2017). Therefore, accurate rheological measurements are essential when
66 developing and manufacturing high-quality products with high repeatability. However, only a few
67 studies to date have investigated the flocculation of CMF suspensions in dynamic flow conditions,
68 and typically the analyses have been performed off-line in a laboratory, while it would be more
69 beneficial to monitor the bulk properties of the CMF suspension, such as viscosity, floc size, and
70 consistency, online in the actual process conditions. Pääkkönen et al. (2016) measured CMF floc size
71 using the dynamic light scattering method (DLS) in stationary conditions with photon correlation
72 spectroscopy. Saarikoski et al. (2012), Karppinen et al. (2012), Saarinen et al. (2014), and Martoïa
73 et al. (2015) carried out CMF flocculation studies by combining a transparent cylindrical rotational
74 rheometer with digital imaging. Raj et al. (2017) used focused beam reflectance measurement
75 (FBRM) by immersing the probe in a stirred CMF suspension.

76 Due to the development of non-invasive flow measurement techniques, velocity profiling has become
77 an important tool for online rheological analysis (Powell 2008). Here, the velocity profile of the
78 studied fluid is measured in laminar flow conditions in a circular pipe in the radial direction. The
79 viscosity at distance z from the wall is then

$$80 \quad \mu(z) = \dot{\gamma}(z)/\tau(z), \quad (2)$$

81 where the local shear rate, $\dot{\gamma}(z)$, is obtained by differentiating the measured velocity profile, $v(z)$, and
82 the shear stress distribution

$$83 \quad \tau(z) = \Delta P(R-z)/2\pi R^2 \Delta l \quad (3)$$

84 is determined from the simultaneously measured pressure drop ΔP over distance Δl (here R is the
85 pipe radius). While magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) is also an option (Arola et al. 1997; Rofe et
86 al. 1996), the most popular method for velocity profiling is ultrasound (UVP), which is widely used
87 in various real-life industrial processes (Derakhshandeh et al. 2010; Takeda 2012; Wunderlich and
88 Brunn 1999).

89 A promising higher-resolution alternative for structural imaging and velocity profiling is optical
90 coherence tomography (OCT). Here, low-coherence, near-infrared light is used to non-destructively
91 probe the reflectivity and speed of the sample as a function of depth (Chen et al. 1997; Drexler and
92 Fujimoto 2008; Huang et al. 1991). By acquiring multiple side-by-side depth profiles (A-scans), a
93 tomographic image of both the structure and the flow field of the sample is obtained. The temporal
94 resolution of OCT is relatively high—tens of thousands of depth profiles can be acquired per second
95 using specific frequency-domain techniques. This makes it possible to acquire sharp images of

96 relatively fast flowing suspensions. The resolution of the images is at the micrometer scale both
97 axially and radially with respect to the probing light beam. The greatest downside of the OCT
98 technique is that the sample must be semi-transparent to the probing light, and even then, the
99 sensitivity of the measurement decreases rapidly with increasing depth. The achievable imaging depth
100 depends strongly on the sample, with typical values being in the range of a few millimeters. Since the
101 thickness of the wall-depletion layer of CMF suspensions is typically rather small, the measurement
102 range of OCT is usually high enough not only to analyze the wall-depletion layer but also the bulk
103 behavior of the studied fluid (Kataja et al. 2017; Lauri et al. 2017). OCT has the advantage over digital
104 imaging, DLS, and FBRM in online measurements due to the fact that it can see beyond the wall-
105 depletion layer and it gives information on both the axial and the radial floc sizes. Moreover, unlike
106 in digital imaging, the optical access window can be small and does not require immersion, like
107 FBRM. Previously, Koponen et al. (2018) demonstrated the use of structural OCT images for
108 analyzing CMF flocculation.

109 In this study, structural OCT data is used to analyze the flocculation behavior of an aqueous
110 suspension of mechanically disintegrated cellulose microfibrils in a pipe flow at three different
111 consistencies (0.4%, 1.0%, and 1.6%). Moreover, the viscous behavior of the suspensions is
112 determined from the OCT velocity profiles. Finally, the study will demonstrate that an apparent
113 attenuation coefficient of the OCT signal can be used to determine the consistency of the CMF
114 suspensions. The results demonstrate that while OCT is quite useful for academic CMF studies, it
115 could also be used as a versatile quality and process control tool for CMF manufacturing and
116 processing.

117 **Materials and methods**

118 *Cellulose microfibrils*

119 The CMFs used in this study are manufactured mechanically from purified wood pulp (Celish® KY-
120 100G, Daicel Chemical Industries, Japan). A polarized light microscope image and SEM image of
121 the CMF are shown in Figures 1a and 1b, respectively. The size distribution of the CMFs is quite
122 wide, making it difficult to accurately and uniquely measure them. Tatsumi et al. (2002) reported an
123 average length and diameter of 350 μm and 15 μm , respectively, for the fibrils, while Kose et al.
124 (2015) obtained an average fibril width of 0.7 μm . Varanasi et al. (2013) analyzed a fine mass fraction
125 of the CMFs and estimated their average width and length to be 70 nm and 9 μm , respectively. For
126 the flow experiments, the original CMF suspension was diluted by deionized water to mass
127 consistencies of 0.4%, 1.0%, and 1.6%.

128

129 **Fig. 1** A polarized light microscope image (a) and SEM image (b) of the CMFs (Haavisto et al. 2011)

130

131

132 **Fig. 2** (a) The measurement configuration. The suspension is pumped from the fluid tank, which includes the flow rate sensor and the temperature control unit. OCT measurements are performed in the loop section, which consists of a glass pipe. The setup also included an ultrasound velocity profiling (UVP) unit. (b) An example of the averaged velocity profile and the corresponding backscattering amplitude from the OCT measurements. The consistency is 0.4% and the flow rate is 24.7 ml/s

138 **Experimental setup**

139 The measurement unit consisted of a 2.5 m long, optical-grade glass pipe with an inner diameter of
 140 $D = 19$ mm (Fig. 2a). Stable flow conditions in the pipe were induced by a low-pulsation, progressive
 141 cavity pump (Seepex MD series). The volume of the sample fluid in the loop, including the tank, was
 142 13.5 l. The fluid temperature in the loop was set as 21°C with a digital temperature controller (Model
 143 9610, PolyScience). The volumetric flow rate in the loop was measured using a magnetic flow rate

144 sensor (Sitrans F M MAGFLO). The measurements were conducted under stationary flow conditions
145 at the flow rate range of 8 ml/s – 169 ml/s. To determine the wall shear stress at each flow rate,
146 pressure drop was measured using a differential pressure sensor along the distance of $\Delta l = 1.0$ m. In
147 addition to the OCT device, the setup included an ultrasound velocity profiling (UVP) unit
148 (DOP2000, Signal-Processing S.A., Switzerland), measurements reported previously by Kataja et al.
149 (2017). The measurement setup has been explained in more detail by Haavisto et al. (2017).

150 *Optical coherence tomography measurements*

151 A commercial spectral domain OCT device (Telesto I SD-OCT, Thorlabs Inc.), operating at a 1325
152 nm center wavelength, was used to structural characterization and viscosity determination of the
153 flowing CMF suspensions. The system has an inherent depth (radial direction, along the probing
154 beam) resolution of approximately 7.5 μm in air and approximately 5.6 μm in water. The lateral (axial
155 direction) resolution is approximately 15 μm . The maximum imaging depth range in air is 2.5 mm,
156 with the A-scan consisting of 512 pixels; thus, the pixel resolution in air is approximately 4.9 μm .

157 The OCT device was set up to perform continuous A-scans through the pipe wall and the suspension,
158 such that the OCT probing beam remained in the same location all the time. The floc structure of the
159 CMF suspension flowing past the OCT probing beam, and its local velocity, was captured in the
160 resulting OCT images. The axial pixel size of the captured data depends on the local flow velocity
161 and the A-scan rate of the OCT device.

162 The A-scan rate was set between 28 kHz and 91 kHz, depending on the flow rate, to avoid phase
163 wrapping in the velocity measurements (Xia et al. 2017). The angle between the OCT probing beam
164 and the flow direction (Doppler angle), used to calculate the axial velocities (Haavisto et al. 2017),
165 was $86.5^\circ \pm 0.2^\circ$, as determined from B-scan images composed of 4096 A-scans in a lateral range of
166 5.00 mm.

167 *Floc size analysis*

168 The floc sizes were determined in the radial (normal to pipe wall) and the axial (along the pipe)
169 directions. The floc size analysis was performed outside the wall depletion layer in the bulk region
170 (see Fig. 2b), where the velocity profile is approximately linear and relatively shallow and the
171 consistency is approximately constant. In the wall depletion region, consistency is an unknown
172 function of the distance from the wall, whereas the steep velocity profile hinders simultaneous
173 determination of the radial floc size and the velocity scaling of the axial floc size. For these reasons,
174 floc analysis would not be reasonable there. The distances from the wall where the bulk region begins
175 were estimated from the onset of the linear part of the flow velocity profile: 150 μm for 0.4% (see

176 Fig. 2b), 100 μm for 1.0%, and 50 μm for 1.6% consistencies. Also, the maximum imaging depth
177 was estimated based on the velocity profile as the point where it began to deviate from the assumed
178 linear profile in the bulk region due to attenuation of the optical signal and decreased signal-to-noise
179 ratio (SNR). The maximum imaging depths were 670 μm for 0.4%, 650 μm for 1.0% and 520 μm for
180 1.6% consistencies.

181 The floc size analysis followed for the most part the method introduced by Koponen et al. (2018).
182 Initially, the depth-dependent decay of the OCT signal must be corrected. The decay is mainly caused
183 by scattering and absorption of photons, fringe washout due to flowing scatterers (Yun et al. 2004),
184 and inherent sensitivity decay of the system due to the finite pixel size of the spectrometer (Leitgeb
185 et al. 2003). The depth-dependent decay was corrected by first calculating the average OCT signal as
186 a function of depth and then scaling the pixel values at a given depth using the inverse of the average.
187 This process ensures that the average OCT signal is equal in the corrected image at each depth.

188
189 **Fig. 3** Average velocity beyond the wall-depletion layer in the bulk region for 1.0% consistency. The
190 black rectangles are from the measured OCT velocity data and the solid lines represent the fitted
191 piecewise linear function. The open circles (only structural data available, flow rate measured) are
192 interpolated from the fits and used to scale the axial dimension in the floc size analysis

193 To reduce granularity in the images, and to account for the different radial and axial resolutions of
194 the OCT setup, the frames were resized to 11 $\mu\text{m} \times 11 \mu\text{m}$ pixels. The native radial pixel size of
195 4.9 μm (in air), the refractive index of water ($n = 1.33$), and the average axial velocity in the bulk
196 region were taken into account in the scaling process. Unfortunately, the OCT velocity data used to
197 calculate the flow velocity profile and the average axial velocity in the bulk region was only available
198 as a separate set of measurements for a reduced number of flow rates. The average velocities in the

199 flocculation measurement region, obtained from the available velocity profiles when plotted as a function of
200 the flow rate, exhibited piecewise linear behavior, probably due to the combined effect of apparent
201 wall slip and shear thinning. The velocities were fitted with piecewise linear functions (1, 2, and 3
202 line segments for 0.4%, 1.0%, and 1.6 % consistencies, respectively) and interpolation was used to
203 estimate the average axial velocities for all the flow rates. Fig. 3 shows the average velocity as a
204 function of flow rate for a 1.0% CMF suspension together with the fitted interpolation function. For
205 improved axial scaling accuracy, both structural and velocity data should be recorded for all the
206 measurements. However, an error in the axial scaling mostly affects the determined floc size, while
207 the trend remains undisturbed.

208 To determine the floc sizes, the resized images were thresholded using Otsu's method (Otsu 1979)
209 instead of the median used by Koponen et al. (2018). The median thresholding assumes that half of
210 the image consists of flocs and the other half of water. Such an assumption can lead to under- or
211 overestimation of the area covered by the flocs, and furthermore, it can break down the flocs at high
212 consistencies and combine them at low consistencies. Fig. 4 shows resized images (upper row) and
213 Otsu-thresholded images (lower row) for all the consistencies at the same flow rate of approximately
214 31 ml/s.

215
216 **Fig. 4** Resized images with a uniform pixel size of 11 μm (upper row) and corresponding Otsu-
217 thresholded images (bottom row) for (a) 0.4%, (b) 1.0%, and (c) 1.6% consistencies. The white color
218 depicts the fibrils and the black corresponds to water. The direction of the flow is from right to left,
219 and only the bulk region is shown

220 The radial and axial floc size distributions were calculated as run-length distributions, in which the
221 run-lengths are the lengths of the longest possible continuous line segments that are completely inside
222 the CMF phase and oriented in the radial and axial directions, respectively. The obtained distribution
223 histogram of run-lengths was weighted by the length and normalized by a sum of length counts.
224 Images were acquired at two different OCT A-scan acquisition rates, 28 kHz and 91 kHz. The SNR

225 is reduced at the 91 kHz A-scan rate compared to the 28 kHz rate. This will cause discrepancies in
 226 thresholding and further in the floc sizes determined from the thresholded images. The discrepancy
 227 exhibits itself as an offset in the floc size values between the two A-scan acquisition rates, and it was
 228 compensated for by scaling the floc sizes acquired at 91 kHz, such that the floc size is approximately
 229 continuous as a function of wall shear stress (see Fig. 5).

230

231 **Fig. 5** The offset between the 28 kHz and 91 kHz scan rates. The offset is compensated for by a
 232 scaling factor that makes the floc size approximately continuous between the scan rates

233

234 **Fig. 6** Pressure loss as a function of the mean velocity

235

236

237

238

239 **Fig. 7** Flow velocity profiles at a similar mean velocity. The solid lines depict linear fitted lines, while
 240 the dashed lines are extensions of the fits. There is apparent shear banding at consistencies of 0.4%
 241 and 1.0%, which is probably caused by increased consistency in this region

242 **Results and discussion**

243 *Viscosity and apparent shear banding*

244 Fig. 6 shows the measured pressure loss in the pipe as a function of the mean velocity. The shape of
 245 the curves resembles that of shear thinning fluids, but the wall slip makes the behavior more complex
 246 (Kataja et al. 2017). Local viscosity of the CMF suspension above the wall-depletion layer can be
 247 directly calculated by utilizing the wall shear stress and the shear rate obtained from the OCT velocity
 248 profile, as explained in the introduction. Since the velocity profile above the wall-depletion layer is
 249 locally approximately linear, the shear rates can be determined by fitting a line on the linear part of
 250 the measured velocity profile (see the solid lines in Fig. 7). The dashed lines in Fig. 7 are extensions
 251 of the linear fits. The fits are located at different distances from the wall. At a consistency of 1.6%,
 252 the signal began to slightly decrease after a 300 μm distance from the wall and was more evident after
 253 500 μm . This was due to strong scattering and attenuation of the signal, which led to low SNR and
 254 unreliable determination of the velocity. Interestingly, at consistencies of 0.4% and 1.0% the velocity
 255 profiles differed from the linear fits at the beginning of the bulk region, which can clearly be seen
 256 from the extensions of the fitted lines (dashed lines). Such a behavior, which was consistently
 257 observed with all flow rates, could be due to a shear banding process, in which a suspension has
 258 localized bands with different viscosities, and thus, shear rates due to a difference in the CMF
 259 structure, for instance in the fibril orientation or flocculation (Nechporchuk et al. 2016). However,
 260 it is more likely that the CMF consistency was slightly higher in this region than in the interior parts

261 of the pipe due to wall depletion, which pushed fibrils and flocs away from the wall. This finding is
 262 substantiated by the fact that the effect was stronger at lower consistencies, which also have a thicker
 263 wall-depletion layer (Koponen et al. 2019). At a consistency of 1.6%, the suspension is probably too
 264 crowded for the migration of individual fibrils and flocs away from the wall. As a result, the
 265 suspension compressed collectively, and the protuberance was not seen in the velocity profile.

266 Fig. 8 shows the viscosity as a function of shear rate. The solid lines show viscosities for the same
 267 CMFs determined with the UVP method in the whole pipe (Koponen et al. 2019). The OCT
 268 viscosities corresponded well with the UVP data. Thus, the actual viscous behavior of the CMF
 269 suspensions can be obtained accurately with OCT in the vicinity of the pipe wall.

270
 271 **Fig. 8** Viscosity as a function of the shear rate. The solid lines show the viscous behavior obtained
 272 with UVP measurements for the same CMFs (Koponen et al. 2019). At a consistency of 1.6%, the
 273 filled data point is close to the yield stress. Here large variation in the measured viscosity can occur,
 274 and thus, it deviates from the general trend

275 For estimating yield stress, τ_y , the fit of the Herschel–Bulkley model $\tau = \tau_y + K\dot{\gamma}^n$ with the shear
 276 stress–shear rate data failed, and the yield stress was estimated using the Casson model
 277 $\tau^{0.5} = \tau_y^{0.5} + a\dot{\gamma}^{0.5}$. The obtained values for the yield stress were 0.5 Pa, 2 Pa, and 9 Pa, for 0.4%, 1.0%
 278 and 1.6% consistencies, respectively. Note that for the lowest shear rate, where the shear stress was
 279 8.5 Pa, *i.e.* slightly below the estimated yield stress, the viscosity of the 1.6% consistency differed
 280 clearly from the general trend (see the filled data point in Fig. 8). Here, the fluctuations around the
 281 yield point through continuous break-up and recovery of the network structure combined with a

282 limited measurement time led to large variations in the measured viscosity (Lauri et al. 2017). We
 283 have omitted this data point in Fig. 11.

284
 285 **Fig. 9** Floc size distributions in the radial direction at consistencies of (a) 0.4%, (c) 1.0%, and (e)
 286 1.6%. Floc size distributions in the axial direction at consistencies of (b) 0.4%, (d) 1.0%, and (f) 1.6%.
 287 The numbers in the legend show the wall shear stress and the flow rate in the pipe

288 **Floc size**

289 Fig. 9 shows the radial and the axial floc size distributions, which exhibit a roughly log-normal shape
 290 common to fibers and fibrils (Hourani 1988a, 1988b; Koponen et al. 2018; Saarikoski et al. 2012)
 291 and many other flocculating particles (Coufort et al. 2008; Shin et al. 2015). At a consistency of 1.6%,
 292 and to some extent also at 1.0%, the measurement range was too short in the radial direction, which
 293 can be noted in the peaks at the highest floc size bins (see Fig. 9 c, e). In the axial direction, the
 294 acquired image length was much longer, and therefore, we obtained undistorted distribution profiles.
 295 However, in order to evaluate and compare floc sizes, we limited the axial distributions to the same
 296 length as the radial distributions. For the average (length-weighted) floc size calculations, we omitted
 297 the peaks at the largest sizes and only used distributions up to the 450 μm for all the cases. Note that

298 most CNF grades are finer than the CNF used here. Thus, their floc size is generally smaller and
 299 complete floc size distributions would be obtained.

300
 301 **Fig. 10** a) Radial and axial floc sizes as a function of shear stress. b) Geometric floc sizes as a function
 302 of shear stress. The lines show power law fits to the measurement points shown with black markers

303 Fig.10a shows the average axial and radial floc sizes as a function of shear stress. The floc size was
 304 systematically smaller in the radial direction when compared to the axial direction. This was the case
 305 also in a study by Koponen et al. (2018) of a finer, mechanically disintegrated CMF at a 0.5%
 306 consistency. The likely reason for this occurrence is that the laminar pipe flow does not experience
 307 elongational (axial) stresses and the flocs are mainly broken by radial shear stress. This could also
 308 explain why the radial floc size decreased monotonically with increasing shear stress at all three
 309 consistencies, while the axial floc size at a consistency of 0.4% remained almost constant and the floc
 310 sizes at consistencies of 1.0% and 1.6% began decreasing monotonically only when a certain shear
 311 stress level was exceeded.

312 Fig. 10b shows the geometric floc size, defined as a square root of the product of the axial and radial
 313 floc sizes and as a function of shear stress. The straight lines are power law fits $L = G\tau^{-\beta}$ to the data,
 314 where G and β are the fitting parameters. The red markers show data points that have been omitted
 315 from the fits (two outliers at a consistency of 0.4%, and the lowest shear stresses at consistencies of
 316 1.0% and 1.6%). We can see that the power law index, $\beta = -0.18$, was the same for all three
 317 consistencies. Thus, the floc rupture dynamics was independent of consistency with higher shear
 318 stresses. Finally, note that the floc size of 0.4% CMFs appeared to saturate at the highest shear
 319 stresses, but the number of data points was too small to draw any real conclusions.

320 The shear thinning behavior of CMF suspensions has been associated with decreasing floc size at an
 321 increasing shear rate or shear stress (Mohtaschemi et al. 2014; Puisto et al. 2012a; 2012b). However,
 322 there is a lack of experimental data to support this assumption. Fig. 11 shows the viscosity and the
 323 geometric floc size as a function of shear stress. We can see that there is a clear similarity between
 324 the floc size and the viscosity. To our knowledge, this data is the most direct evidence to date of the
 325 relationship between the CMF suspension viscosity and floc size. Note that while a power law gives
 326 a good approximation of the viscous behavior of the CMFs (see Fig. 8), the viscous behavior is in
 327 reality more complex. At a consistency of 1.0%, and especially 1.6%, the viscosity-shear stress data
 328 consist of two groups separated by a transition region. Similar viscosity behavior has also been noted
 329 by Lauri et al. (2017) for a finer CMF at a 0.5% consistency. The most obvious reason for such an
 330 abrupt change in the rheological behavior of the CMF suspension would be a sudden structural change
 331 in the suspension, for example in the fibril orientation (Mykhaylyk et al. 2016) and/or flocculation
 332 (Bounoua et al. 2016). Indeed, the floc size at a consistency of 1.0% follows rather consistently the
 333 viscosity behavior. However, at a consistency of 1.6% the floc size cannot explain the abrupt drop in
 334 viscosity at the shear stress of 20 Pa. The changes in the floc aspect ratio (data not shown) were also
 335 too small to explain the observed behavior. It is possible that, for instance, concentration variations
 336 in the measurement region due to the wall depletion and subsequent compression of the 1.6% CMFs
 337 caused this to occur, but a clear explanation for the observed viscous behavior is currently lacking.

338
 339 **Fig. 11** Geometric floc size and viscosity as a function of the shear stress (log-log scale)

340 ***Consistency and OCT attenuation coefficient***

341 The change in the consistency can be qualitatively estimated based on the OCT amplitude signal. A
 342 quantitative analysis is possible by utilizing an attenuation coefficient, the slope of the decaying signal

343 (Gong et al. 2020; Vermeer et al. 2013), and predefined suspension consistencies for calibration.
344 Multiple different factors in a measured sample influence the amplitude of an OCT signal. A large
345 difference in refractive indexes between a scatterer and surrounding media increases the reflectivity
346 and leads to a higher signal amplitude. In addition, higher particle concentration or, in this case, higher
347 fibril consistency results in increased signal amplitude. On the other hand, a dense packing of
348 scatterers can lead to dependent scattering, which will decrease the backscattered light intensity, and
349 thus, the signal amplitude (Almasian et al. 2015; Kalkman et al. 2010). Other influencing factors, in
350 addition to those already mentioned in the Materials and methods section, include particle size, the
351 scattering anisotropy of the suspension, multiple scattering, and the depth of field of the focusing
352 optics (Almasian et al. 2015; Kholodnykh et al. 2003; Thrane et al. 2000; Yadlowsky et al. 1995).
353 There have been studies to estimate the concentration of spherical particles in static (Hillman et al.
354 2006; Sugita et al. 2016) and flow (Wang and Wang 2011) conditions via statistical analyses of the
355 OCT amplitude signal. Such studies typically used homogenous suspension with monodispersed
356 particle size; however, due to the complex size and shape distribution of CMFs, the direct
357 applicability of the proposed theoretical formalisms should first be verified with simulations.

358 Decay of the OCT signal can be used to estimate an attenuation coefficient, which includes the effects
359 of both scattering and absorption. It has been demonstrated that in the single scattering regime, the
360 OCT intensity signal can be estimated by a Beer's law using a single exponential decay function

$$361 \quad I(z) = I_0 e^{-2u_t z}, \quad (4)$$

362 where z is the depth coordinate, I_0 is the incident intensity, and u_t is the attenuation coefficient (Faber
363 et al. 2004; Schmitt et al. 1993; Smithies et al. 1998). A factor of two in the exponent accounts for
364 the roundtrip attenuation. In the present study, an apparent attenuation coefficient was determined by
365 fitting the single exponential function with two variables (attenuation and intensity) to the linear part
366 (in a log scale) of the OCT intensity signal (see Fig. 12a). Due to nonhomogeneous suspension, the
367 fitting was performed at the highest flow rates to ensure reasonable sample length, and thus, good
368 averaging of the data. A linear relationship of the obtained apparent attenuation coefficients and the
369 CMF consistency is shown in Fig. 12b. The term "apparent" is used here because the sensitivity decay
370 of the OCT system was not considered in the calculation and the absolute intensity values are not
371 known. Due to the unknown intensity range of the OCT signal, the absolute coefficient values are
372 only relative. However, they are expected to be at the upper limit, and the actual attenuation
373 coefficients would then be smaller. This is because the single scattering approximation and the linear
374 relationship between the attenuation coefficient and the consistency typically applies only in the

375 weakly scattering regime, $u_t < 5\text{-}10 \text{ mm}^{-1}$ (Almasian et al. 2015; Faber et al. 2004; Kalkman et al.
 376 2010). Nevertheless, the relative scattering coefficients are sufficient for monitoring consistency at
 377 the online conditions since the calibration slope (Fig. 12b) must always be determined in advance for
 378 each CMF suspension.

379
 380 **Fig. 12** (a) OCT signal measured at consistencies 0.4%, 1%, and 1.6% (the solid lines are the fitted
 381 exponentials, $I(z)=Ae^{-2Bz}$, in which A and B are the fitting parameters). (b) The apparent attenuation
 382 coefficients (the fit parameter B) as a function of the CMF consistency (the solid line is a linear fit to
 383 the data points)

384 Conclusions

385 In this work, we applied OCT to analyze the viscous and structural properties of CMF suspensions at
 386 consistencies of 0.4%, 1.0%, and 1.6%. The measured viscosities agreed quite well with ultrasound
 387 velocity profiling performed for the same CMFs. Interestingly, the measured velocity profiles of the
 388 0.4% and 1.0% CMFs showed apparent shear banding just above the wall depletion layer, which was
 389 manifested as a protuberance deviating from the generally linear velocity profile. This was probably
 390 caused by wall depletion, which pushed fibrils and flocs away from the wall, thereby increasing the
 391 local consistency of the suspension.

392 The structural OCT images were used to calculate the radial and axial floc sizes of the suspension.
 393 Floc size was systematically smaller in the radial direction than in the axial direction, most likely
 394 because the laminar pipe flow did not exhibit elongational (axial) stresses and the flocs were mainly
 395 broken by radial shear stress. A fit of a power law to geometrical floc size–shear stress data gave the
 396 same power law index for all consistencies. This suggests that floc rupture dynamics is independent
 397 of consistency. Comparison of the dependence of viscosity and floc size as a function of shear stress
 398 showed clear similarities. This result supports the hypothesis that the flow dynamics of the CMF

399 suspensions are those of flocs and not individual fibrils and that the shear thinning behavior of CMF
400 suspensions is closely related to decreasing floc size.

401 An apparent attenuation coefficient of the structural OCT signal was determined by fitting an
402 exponential function with two variables (attenuation and intensity) to it. We determined an accurate
403 linear relationship between the obtained apparent attenuation coefficients and the CMF consistencies.

404 Earlier studies have shown that OCT is an excellent tool for analyzing the flow dynamics of the CMF
405 wall depletion layer. In this work, we demonstrated that OCT is quite useful also for analyzing the
406 bulk properties of CMF suspensions, including viscosity, floc size, and consistency. The versatility
407 of OCT makes it a multi-purpose tool not only for academic studies, but potentially also for industrial
408 process and quality control.

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